

Formulation And Evaluation of Isoniazid Medicated Candy for Pediatric Patient

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ABSTRACT

The therapy for tuberculosis (TB) has a number of issues with compliance, specifically with children, who simply do not enjoy the present drugs. Although the main concern of this study was the formulation and an assessment of a child-friendly palatable medicated hard candy of Isoniazid, in order to enhance tolerability, compliance and adherence to TB therapy can significantly improve with a better drug formulation. Eight (F1-F8) formulations of Isoniazid hard candy medicated were formulated and optimized through a hard candy (heat and congealing method) with different polymer blends of Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), Methyl cellulose and Sodium Carboxymethylcellulose (Na-CMC). Pre-formulation studies ensured the identity and purity of the medication establish a melting point of 170.3°C and maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) of 263nm. The Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) established Isoniazid "in-use" compatibility with chosen excipients. The physical attributes of the candy were hard, red and within an acceptable level of tolerability and palatability. Hardness and friability testing showed adequate mechanical strength with acceptable hardness values of 15.6 to 18.3 kg/cm² and friability of 0.12% to 0.35%. Studies on In vitro release were conducted and the rate of release for most of the formulations were well fit by the Korsmeyer-Peppas model with the high correlation coefficient (R^2) values of nearly 0.9997. Release exponent (n) values were more than 1, pointing towards An enhanced case-II transport mechanism The present study revealed successful formulation of a stable medicated candy of Isoniazid with suitable properties such as the taste, appearance and delivery system.

Keywords: Isoniazid, Tuberculosis (TB), Medicated Candy, Pediatric, Patient Compliance

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is a long-standing infectious illness caused by Mycobacterium tuberculosis, which primarily affects the lungs. Transmission occurs through aerosols expelled when an infected individual speaks, sneezes, or coughs. If left untreated, TB can be fatal; however, with the appropriate antibiotic regimen, it is largely curable. In many countries, newborns Bacille Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccination is administered to young children as a preventative strategy against severe forms of the disease. Several factors elevate susceptibility to TB, including diabetes, HIV/AIDS, undernutrition, smoking, and excessive alcohol intake¹. Preventive therapy for TB (TPT), such as a six-month isoniazid

course, has proven effective for individuals in close contact with confirmed TB patients and for people living with HIV^{2,3}. According to the India TB Report 2024, children aged 0-14 years account for approximately 6-8% of total reported TB cases⁴. Furthermore, the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023) notes that India contributes to about one-third of the global childhood TB burden⁵, with an estimated 188 incidents per 100,000 kids per year⁶. TB can present in several clinical forms. Pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) is the most prevalent and infectious type, typically characterized by a persistent cough, fever, weight loss, and sometimes hemoptysis, and diagnosed through sputum examination and chest imaging⁷. Extrapulmonary tuberculosis (EPTB), which impacts organs other than the lungs, including

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the central nervous system, lymph nodes, pleura, and bones, and the genitourinary tract—accounts for roughly 15-25% of all TB cases^{8,9}. Latent TB infection (LTBI) occurs when bacteria remain dormant inside granulomas, whereas active TB manifests once immune control is lost, allowing bacterial replication^{10,11}. Drug-resistant TB (DR-TB) represents forms of the disease that no longer respond to standard treatment drugs, including mono-resistant, multi-drug-resistant (MDR), pre-XDR, and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) TB¹². Standard TB therapy includes first-line medications such as ethambutol, pyrazinamide, rifampicin, and isoniazid. However, administering these drugs to pediatric patients often poses challenges, as conventional tablets may be difficult for them to swallow, which can reduce adherence. This limitation has stimulated interest in novel dosage forms—such as orally disintegrating tablets, thin films, and medicated candies—to improve compliance and therapeutic outcomes. Among various innovative options, oral transmucosal delivery provides notable advantages. It allows drugs to enter systemic circulation directly via the oral mucosa, avoiding the first-pass metabolism of the liver and enhancing absorption rates¹³. The oral cavity contains distinct mucosal regions—buccal, sublingual, and gingival—each differing in permeability and structure¹⁴. The buccal mucosa is particularly favourable for medication administration because of its rich blood supply, non-keratinized surface, and patient comfort during administration. Saliva, continuously secreted at a rate of approximately 0.5-2 liters per day, keeps the mucosa hydrated and assists in dissolving and transporting drugs¹⁵. The vascular network beneath the buccal mucosa, drained by the internal jugular vein and supplied by branches of the external carotid artery, facilitates direct entry of the drug into systemic circulation¹⁶. The mucus layer, composed primarily of mucin glycoproteins, provides a protective and lubricating barrier that also influences drug diffusion and absorption^{17,18}. Absorption happens mostly through passive diffusion over the oral mucosa, involving two pathways: transcellular (through cells) and paracellular (between cells)^{19,20}. Lipophilic drugs favor the transcellular route, while hydrophilic molecules generally traverse intercellular spaces. Several parameters—such as mucosal thickness, lipid content, drug solubility, and formulation design—

govern the efficiency of absorption. Oral mucosal delivery systems offer key benefits, including enhanced patient compliance, avoidance of gastrointestinal degradation, and reduced enzymatic breakdown compared with conventional oral dosage forms²¹. Nevertheless, challenges persist, such as limited surface area for absorption, dilution of drugs by saliva, the need for effective taste masking, and the risk of mucosal irritation²². Medicated candies have recently emerged as appealing oral dosage forms designed to slowly melt or break down in the mouth, allowing either local or systemic therapeutic action²³. They are prepared by incorporating the active pharmaceutical ingredient into a sweetened base, making them especially suitable for children, elderly patients, and individuals with swallowing difficulties. These formulations can improve bioavailability, mask unpleasant tastes, and bypass first-pass metabolism while offering controlled or sustained release^{24,25}. However, their development requires careful formulation strategies to address potential risks such as accidental ingestion by children, incompatibility with aldehyde-based excipients, and instability of drugs sensitive to heat during manufacturing^{26,27}.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Isoniazid and Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose were from LOBA CHEMIE PVT. LTD and Sucrose, Dextrose, Methylcellulose, Sodium-Carboxymethylcellulose and Citric acid were from Sd-fine chem limited.

Methods

Preformulation studies:

The initial stage in the process was pre-formulation studies, logical formation of any phrase. It is the study of the physical and chemical characteristics of the medication active ingredients both by themselves and in conjunction with excipients. The physicochemical characteristics of the new emulsion that could be influence the development of medication expression and efficacy. Pre-expression testing's primary goal is to generate data that will assist the developer in creating stable and bioavailable capsule forms.

- To identify physical attributes.
- To ascertain the excipient's compatibility.

Characterization, Isoniazid

Organoleptic characteristics:

The medication powder's color, taste, and odour were assessed.

Solubility Characteristics:

A solubility assessment is performed by progressively adding little portions of the solute to a predetermined volume of various solvents. The mixture is thoroughly agitated and inspected for any undissolved particles following each addition.

Melting point:

Melting point, Isoniazid was determined using the open capillary method. This test serves as an initial indicator of the sample's purity, as even small amounts of impurities can be detected through a lowering and broadening of the melting point range. Heating was commenced and recorded the drug's melting point temperature. For the average reading, the procedure was performed three times.

Determination of λ max:

Using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer, which scans wavelengths between 200 and 400 nm, the UV absorption spectrum of isoniazid was captured. At a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, isoniazid dissolved in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) produced a typical spectrum²⁸.

Determination of standard calibration curve:

Stock 1: 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Isoniazid was made by dissolving 100 mg of medication in 100 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) in a volumetric flask.

Stock 2: From the stock 1 solution pipette out 10 ml of solution and diluted to 100 ml in a 100 volumetric flask filled with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

Serial dilution:

- Pipette out 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 1.8, 2.0, 2.2 ml of the stock 2 solution, then dilute it with Phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), 10 ml.
- A concentration of 4, 8, 12, 16, 18, 20 and 22 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ can be obtained from the stock 2 solution. At 263 nm, the absorbance of the diluted solutions was measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer.
- Plotting the solution's concentration, X axis and the absorbance, Y axis allowed for creation a calibration curve, and correlation " r^2 " was computed²⁹.

FT-IR Spectroscopy-Based Drug and Excipient Compatibility Studies

Compatibility tests were performed to look into potential interactions between isoniazid and the excipients used in drug formulation. The drug excipients were physically mixed for evaluating their suitability. Both drug and drug-excipient mixture's infrared spectra were examined within the 400-4000 cm^{-1} wavelength.

The sample disc was made by mixing approximately 1 or 2 ml of the sample material with 10-20 ml of potassium bromide (KBr). The resulting mixture was then compressed using a hydraulic press to create a thin disc that was about 10-15 mm in diameter. This was enough to provide an infrared spectrum with an appropriate intensity. After that, the disc was put in a sample holder and scanned in an FT-IR spectrophotometer between 4000-400 cm^{-1} to obtain a spectrum. To check for any significant interactions, the drug and excipient spectra were compared and their functional group peaks were interpreted³⁰.

Preparation of isoniazid hard medicated candy by heat & congealing method

To prepare the sugar syrup, sugar was mixed with water. A modest amount of water was used to dissolve the dextrose, which was then gradually raised to 110°C until it fully dissolved into a clear, thick syrup. The dextrose solution was added to the sugar syrup, and the mixture was raised to 160°C until it turned a golden yellow color. Once the desired color was achieved, the temperature was reduced to 90°C, and

the medication, polymer, and other components were incorporated. Next, the mixture was transferred into molds. to set. After the tablets were formed, they were

stored in desiccators after being wrapped in aluminum foil to protect them from moisture³¹.

Table No 1: Formulation Table of Isoniazid medicated Candy

SI NO	INGREDIENTS (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	Isoniazid	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
2	Sucrose	2512.5	2466	2450	2416.5	2416	2400	2383	2400
3	Dextrose	1187	1185	1175	1158	1158	1150	1141	1150
4	HPMC-K100	12.5	25	50	-	-	25	50	25
5	Methylcellulose	-	-	-	100	-	100	100	-
6	Na-CMC	-	-	-	-	100	-	-	100
7	Citric acid	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
8	TOTAL (mg)	3700	3700	3700	3700	3700	3700	3700	3700

Evaluations of isoniazid hard medicated candy

Organoleptic properties:

The medicated candy was examined for its color, surface texture, stickiness and mold release property²⁸.

Hardness test:

A precision Monsanto hardness tester was used to determine the candy's hardness. kg/cm² is the measuring unit. Three candies were chosen at random and the candies hardness was assessed³².

Thickness test:

A micrometer can be used to measure the crown thickness of a single candy. Sliding caliper scales can be used to measure the overall crown thickness. Candy thickness should be in between $\pm 5\%$ of the specified norm. To measure thickness, Vernier Calipers were used. The average thickness was determined using ten individual candies from each batch³¹.

Weight variation test:

A digital balance was used to weigh each of the 20 candies that were selected, both individually and collectively. The total weight was used to calculate the average weight. After then the mass of each sweet was compared to the average weight to make sure it was within acceptable limits³³.

$$\text{Average weight} = \frac{\text{Weight of 20 candy}}{20}$$

$$\% \text{Weight variation} = \frac{\text{Average weight} - \text{Weight of each candy}}{\text{Average weight}} \times 100$$

Friability:

The sample were first weighed and put in a friability tester to determine their friability. The apparatus was then operated for four minutes at a 25 rpm speed. After completion of the test, the candies were removed and reweighed to evaluate any weight loss³¹

$$\% \text{ weight loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Drug content:

100 mg of AMT was added to a 100 ml volumetric flask. And equivalent candy after it had been weighed. A small amount of phosphate buffer (6.8) was applied to this to dissolve it. For about fifteen minutes, it was agitated periodically, then phosphate buffer (6.8) was added to bring the volume up to 100 ml. A Whattmann filter paper was used to filter the mixture. After diluting the filtrate with phosphate buffer (6.8), At 263 nm, the absorbance was measured. with phosphate buffer (6.8) serving as a blank. There were six repetitions of this test (N=4)³⁴.

In-vitro dissolution study:

The USP paddle Type II devices were maintained 37 °C \pm 0.5 °C and 50 rpm for the in-vitro dissolution

investigation using 900ml of dissolving liquid. After 5,10,15,20,25 and 30 minutes, 1ml of the sample should be removed and diluted with 10 ml in a volumetric flask. The sink condition is then maintained by replacing the sample with new medium. Using a UV spectrophotometer or an appropriate analytical technique, the drug content of the sample was ascertained. After determining absorbance, the percentage of drug release was computed³⁵.

Stability studies:

For a month, isoniazid-medicated confectionery was tested for stability at room temperature, or 25^o2°C and 85±5% relative humidity. After 1 month drug content, colour, pH and thickness content were determined³¹.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation studies

Characterization of the drug

Organoleptic characterization

Table 2: Organoleptic characterization of Isoniazid

SI.NO	TEST	OBSERVATION
1	Colour	White crystalline powder
2	Odour	Odorless
3	Taste	Bitter
4	pH	6.0-8.0

Solubility Analysis:

Table 3: Solubility profile of Isoniazid

SI.NO	Solvent	Inference
1	Water	Freely soluble
2	Phosphate buffer pH-6.8	Soluble
3	0.1N HCl	Soluble
4	Ether	Very slightly soluble
5	Chloroform	Slightly soluble
6	Ethanol	Soluble

The medication was shown to be soluble in ethanol, water, phosphate buffer pH 6.8, chloroform, and very slightly in ether when its solubility in 10 mg/10 ml of solvent was tested.

Melting point of Isoniazid

Using the capillary method, the melting point was determined to be 170.3°C.

Table 4: Melting point of Isoniazid

Melting Point			
I Trail	II Trail	III Trail	Average
171°C	169°C	171°C	170.3°C

Determination of λ max of Isoniazid

263 nm was determined to be the isoniazid's maximum absorbance. For the purpose of analyzing the medication in dissolving fluid, a wavelength of 263 nm was used.

Fig-1 UV spectrum of Isoniazid

Standard calibration curve of Isoniazid

Fig-2 Standard Curve of Isoniazid

Beer-Lambert's law was adhered to by the analytical approach in this inquiry. In the concentration range of 4 to 22 µg/ml and it worked well for estimating Isoniazid with 0.1 M HCL. The value of correlation coefficient (R^2) for the linear regression equation determined to be 0.9999. This shows a positive relationship between the drug concentration and the associated absorbance readings.

FT-IR Analysis:

FT-IR spectra of Isoniazid:

Fig.3: FT-IR Spectra of Isoniazid

FT-IR Spectra of Isoniazid with Sucrose + Dextrose + HPMC + Na-CMC + MC + Citric acid:

Fig.4 FT-IR Spectra of Isoniazid with Sucrose + Dextrose + HPMC + Na-CMC + MC + Citric acid

Characterization of prepared medicated candy:

Evaluation of Isoniazid medicated Candy

Table 5: Appearance of medicated candy

Formulation	Appearance
F1-F8	Red, hard, little sticky, easily removed by mold

Weight Variation:

Table 6: Weight variation of medicated candy

Sl.NO	F1(gm)	F2(gm)	F3(gm)	F4(gm)	F5(gm)	F6(gm)	F7(gm)	F8(gm)
1	3.65	3.6	3.66	3.63	3.93	3.6	3.99	3.94
2	3.467	3.75	3.79	3.74	3.54	3.98	3.83	4.13
3	3.47	3.42	3.77	3.75	3.93	3.98	3.96	3.71
4	3.35	3.9	3.68	3.7	3.91	3.59	4.43	3.55
5	3.84	3.42	3.53	3.58	3.9	3.79	4.55	3.62
6	3.71	3.77	3.74	3.68	3.95	4.06	3.75	4.22
7	3.95	3.89	3.87	3.96	3.82	4.04	4.09	3.86
8	3.6	3.68	3.53	3.59	3.77	4.02	4.09	3.81
9	3.62	3.74	3.98	3.68	4.13	3.51	3.72	4.24
10	3.79	4.03	3.46	3.65	4.66	3.66	3.71	3.56
Average	3.644±0.1851	3.72±0.199	3.7±0.163	3.69±0.109	3.95±0.290	3.82±0.216	4.01±0.290	3.86±0.263

Fig-5: Medicated candy

Table 7: Thickness, friability, Hardness, Drug content of medicated candy

Formulation	Thickness (mm) ± S.D	Hardness (kg/cm ²) ± S.D	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)
F1	8.74±0.4115	15.6±0.577	0.19	106.9
F2	8.54±0.3366	16±1.000	0.16	96
F3	9.56±0.1244	15.6±1.155	0.24	85.8
F4	9.44±0.1310	15.6±1.155	0.35	81.6
F5	10.14±0.3484	17±1.000	0.32	106.6
F6	10.11±0.5084	16.6±1.155	0.13	80.8
F7	10.41±0.2960	17.6±0.577	0.12	80.2
F8	9.94±0.2319	18.3±0.577	0.28	96.8

Hardness:

All of the candy formulations had hardness levels between 15.6 and 18.3 kg/cm². Out of the eight candy formulations F1, F3, and F4 had the lowest hardness value (15.6 kg/cm²) and F8 had the highest (18.3 kg/cm²). The inclusion of sodium-carboxy methyl cellulose is what gives the candy its hardness.

Thickness:

Every batch of candy was examined and found to be crack-free. Using a Vernier caliper, the candy's thickness was determined and it ranged from 8.54 mm to 10.41 mm, with only minor variations between formulations. This means the candies are fairly uniform.

Weight variation:

Formulations F1, F2, F3, F4, F6, and F8 passed because all candies were within the allowed $\pm 10\%$ weight limit. F5 and F7 failed since two candies went beyond this range. According to IP, only up to two slight variations are allowed, but none should exceed double the limit.

Friability:

All medicated candy formulations showed friability within acceptable limits, indicating they are strong and resistant to breaking or chipping during handling. As per Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP), friability should be not more than 1% weight loss. Since all values were below this limit, the candies passed the friability test successfully.

Drug content:

Formulations F1, F2, F5, and F8 passed as all candies of the following formulations were within the allowed $\pm 10\%$ (i.e. 90 to 110% of label claim) drug content limit. F3, F4, F6 and F7 failed since these formulations went beyond range, as per Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP 2022, General Chapter – Uniformity of Content / Assay of Tablets & Capsules): “The drug content should be within 90.0% to 110.0% of the label claim.

Evaluation of drug content uniformity of isoniazid medicated candy (10mg)

Table 8: Content Uniformity of Isoniazid medicated candy (n = 10)

Formulation	\bar{x} (%label claim)	<i>M</i>	<i>s</i>	AV
F1	100.48	100.48	1.393	3.3432
F2	97.55	98.5	5.66	14.53
F3	95.663	98.5	8.68	23.669
F4	99.60	99.6	5.46	13.10
F5	92.59	98.5	7.80	24.63
F6	100.08	100.08	8.26	19.82
F7	98.79	98.79	5.71	13.7
F8	95.98	98.5	4.12	12.41

Content Uniformity Interpretation:

The content uniformity test results show that F1, F2, F4, F7 and F8 are within 85–115% of label claim and the calculated AV is less than 15. Hence, these batch comply with USP <905> requirements for content uniformity.

Whereas F3, F5 and F6 does not comply with the USP <905> requirements for content uniformity.

In-Vitro Drug Release Studies:

Drug release behaviour was evaluated using 900 ml of dissolution medium, initially followed by phosphate buffer (pH 6.8), under sink conditions in a USP dissolution apparatus type II. Assessing the theoretical release profile is essential for understanding whether the formulation releases the drug at the intended rate and in a controlled manner.

In- Vitro drug release study

Fig-6 Zero order drug release kinetics for F1 - F8 formulation

Fig-7 First Order drug release kinetics for F1 - F8 formulation

Fig-8 Higuchi drug release kinetics for F1 - F8 formulation

Fig-9 Kosermeier - Peppas of F1 - F8 Formulation

Release Kinetics of Formulation F1-F8

Table 9: Regression coefficient (R²) values of kinetics model for formulation F1-F8

Code	RELEASE					Best Fit Model
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Korsmeyer-Peppas		
	R ²	R ²	R ²	R ²	Slope(n)	
F1	0.9969	0.9383	0.9407	0.9997	1.284	Korsmeyer-Peppas Non-Fickian Diffusion
F2	0.9959	0.9188	0.9598	0.9982	1.4258	Korsmeyer-Peppas Non-Fickian Diffusion
F3	0.9973	0.942	0.9431	0.9996	1.2096	Korsmeyer-Peppas Non-Fickian Diffusion
F4	0.9945	0.9452	0.9306	0.9991	1.2673	Korsmeyer-Peppas Non-Fickian Diffusion
F5	0.9936	0.8881	0.9766	0.9872	1.4121	Zero- Order Non-Fickian Diffusion
F6	0.9978	0.9011	0.973	0.9925	1.3574	Zero- Order Non-Fickian Diffusion
F7	0.9889	0.9546	0.9147	0.9985	1.1695	Korsmeyer-Peppas Non-Fickian Diffusion
F8	0.9716	0.9845	0.8777	0.9669	0.9005	First order Non-Fickian Diffusion

Diffusion tests were conducted in-vitro for ten minutes. The F1, F2, F3, F4, and F7 formulations' regression coefficients correspond to the Korsmeyer-Peppas drug release categories. The F8 formulation follows to first-order drug release, while the F5 and F6 formulations follow zero-order drug release. For F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6, F7, and F8, the "n" value derived from the Korsmeyer-Peppas equation was more than 0.5, indicating that the dose formulation demonstrates drug release via a Non-Fickian diffusion mechanism. The optimal formulation (F2) follows to Korsmeyer-Peppas drug release types, and the Korsmeyer-Peppas equation's "n" value was greater than 0.5, indicating non-Fickian diffusion mechanism drug release.

In-vitro drug release of selected F2 formulation:

Fig-10 Zero order drug release selected F2 formulation

Stability studies:

The ideal formulation (F2) performed stability tests at room temperature (25°C±2°C and 85±5%RH).

Stability data of selected F2 formulation stored at room temperature (25°C±2°C and 85±5%RH)

Table 10: Physicochemical parameter of best F2 Formulation at 0, 1st month

No. of days	Physical appearance	Thickness	%Drug content	%Drug release
0	No change	8.54±0.3366	96	97.6 (10 min)
30	No change	8.74±0.4366	95.97	97.3 (10 min)
60	No change	8.68±0.3661	95.87	96.9 (10 min)
90	No change	8.70±0.5322	95.47	96.6 (10 min)

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated an innovative Isoniazid medicated hard candy designed to provide a palatable, stable and child-friendly dosage form for the treatment of tuberculosis. The formulation approach effectively masked the bitterness of Isoniazid and produced a product with acceptable taste, texture and appearance suitable for pediatric use. Physicochemical evaluations confirmed satisfactory hardness (15.6-18.3 kg/cm²), low friability (0.12-0.35%) and uniform weight distribution. Drug content uniformity tests showed that most formulations complied with pharmacopeial standards, with the optimized batch (F2) showing outstanding homogeneity and a 98–100% drug content. *In-Vitro* dissolution studies revealed rapid and complete medication release, with F2 showing the highest release (≈98% within 30 minutes). Kinetic analysis indicated that the release pattern was best explained by the Korsmeyer-Peppas model ($R^2 \approx 0.999$) and the release exponent ($n > 1$) suggested a super case-II transport system controlled by polymer relaxation and erosion. *FTIR* analysis confirmed the absence of any significant drug-excipient interactions, validating formulation stability and compatibility. The optimized Isoniazid hard candy exhibited desirable physicochemical characteristics, predictable release behaviour and excellent palatability, making it a promising and patient-compliant dosage form for pediatric tuberculosis therapy. The study concludes that medicated hard candy can serve as an effective alternative to conventional oral formulations, improving both therapeutic compliance and acceptability in children. However, further studies involving stability testing under ICH conditions, in

vivo pharmacokinetic evaluation and palatability assessments in clinical settings are recommended to establish its long-term safety, efficacy and commercial viability.

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